

Epistemic craftwork, or when is good journalism bad public relations?

Abstract

In April 2007, Seung-Hui Cho mailed a video, several photographs and a lengthy written document to NBC News while in the middle of his infamous shooting spree at Virginia Tech. NBC News president Steve Capus decided to air the footage, which unleashed a torrent of criticism from citizens, law enforcement, commentators, and even Capus' fellow news executives at the other networks. I examine the argumentative exchange between Capus and his colleagues for clues about the professional ideal and expectations in the field of journalism. I unpack Capus' summary formulation of his decision, "Sometimes good journalism is bad public relations," to use the journalism/public relations nexus as a lens for examining the decision pressures faced by a broadcast news executive.

On April 18, 2007, NBC Nightly News included in its broadcast a video clip just over two minutes in length. The video was not the work of any NBC reporter or producer; rather, it had arrived in the mail, part of a multimedia package that included photographs and a written manifesto. Treating it as a tasty exclusive, NBC burned its logo into the video before sharing it with other networks, and included the material in all its regular updates, including its 24 hour news channel, MSNBC. Just forty-eight hours previous, Seung-Hui Cho had murdered thirty-two Virginia Tech students, wounded twenty-five more, and then turned the gun on himself. The video, photos and written remarks were all his work (Carter, 2007; Ruane & Jenkins, 2007).

Public reaction to the broadcast of Cho's message was explosive. Family members of the shooting victims canceled appearances on NBC news programs (Lauer & Vieira, 2007). Kristin Fleming-Dahl, a Virginia Tech sophomore, complained, "It was very scary because it's the closest we're ever going to get to seeing what [the people at Norris Hall] saw. For some of them, that were [sic] their last moments. Seeing the pictures made it more real. It was like a slap in the face ... It probably would have been better to wait" (Ruane & Jenkins, 2007, p. A01). Law enforcement officials objected that the video gave Cho exactly what he wanted, as well as encouraging any others who might consider a similar spree. Virginia State Police superintendent Steve Flaherty announced, "We're rather disappointed in the editorial decision to broadcast these disturbing images. I'm sorry you were all exposed" (Harper, 2007, p. A17), and Michael Mason, head of the FBI criminal investigation division, said that the broadcast "feeds into exactly what he wanted to accomplish by this heinous act" (Ruane & Jenkins, 2007, p. A01). The refrain was taken up almost immediately by talk radio hosts, led by Hugh Hewitt, who labeled the decision "the incentivizing of mass murder, and NBC will have blood on its hands the next time someone sends a video to their network of their mayhem" (Kurtz & O'Brien, 2007, ¶ 27). The American

Psychological Association released an open letter begging NBC to discontinue the coverage (APA urges, 2007), and Accuracy In Media expressed its intention to attend NBC's annual shareholders meeting and call for the firing of its news division president, Steve Capus (AIM editor, 2007).

Complaints from those outside the profession were part of any normal day at the office, but then NBC news anchors began to mention their own misgivings on camera. *Nightly News* anchor Brian Williams introduced the video with a disclaimer: "We are sensitive to how all of this will be seen by those affected, and we know we are, in effect, airing the words of a murderer here tonight" (Williams, 2007, ¶ 2), and during the next morning's *Today Show* broadcast, co-host Matt Lauer remarked, "...it puts us in an unusual and uncomfortable position ... let's be honest, there are some--there are some big differences of opinion right within this news division as to whether we should be airing this stuff at all, whether we're taking the right course of action" (Lauer & Vieira, 2007, ¶¶ 3, 5), an unscripted remark which caught the news division management by surprise (Kurtz, 2007b). Once respected journalists within the organization voiced their own misgivings, NBC had little choice but to address the controversy.

Argument and the professional identity of a journalist

Argumentation scholarship has grown through early acknowledgments that arguments are entangled with an arguer's *identity* (Ehninger, 1970; Kline, 1986; Antczak, 1990), and that during the unfolding of argument, collective identities are shaped and renewed (Hazen & Williams, 1997; McKerrow & Bruner, 1997), to preliminary apprehension of the formative influence of argument on the *shared* identity of practitioners of a profession (Srader, 2007). In particular, the *points of stasis* in intra-professional argument may capture turning points in which

enduring controversies are recast and rechanneled, and in those argumentative contacts reside much of the profession's collective understanding of its ethics, as bound up in its identity.

Within journalism, these answers are particularly elusive, given how many of the field's opinion leaders disagree, sometimes bitterly, about whether it is a profession at all. Several examiners (McQuarrie, 1999; Bishop, 2004; McNay, 2008) found *some* commonalities between journalism and other recognized professions, but conceded that the match fell short of perfection. And Merrill (1986) urged outright rejection of any connection, arguing that

Journalism today, I maintain, is one of the most open and diversified institutions in the country – one that is largely dedicated to public service. I want it to stay that way. But there is the danger that it will become a profession, thereby changing into a narrow, monolithic, self-centered fellowship of true believers devoid of an outward-looking and service orientation (p. 59).

Hampton (2005) reports that “Conceptions of the journalist as ‘professional’ and as practitioner of a ‘craft’ competed for much of the twentieth century” (p. 138). He explains that while some respected journalists argue in favor of formalizing the socialization of reporters and the everyday practice of reporting, others view it as an unteachable talent that is best served if it is not reduced to recipe, and if minimal expectations of conformity are imposed on reporters. The trait of *normative collegiality*, the idea that gives rise to peer review, thus waxes and wanes through journalism's history and among its most influential voices. Some insist that only reporters and editors are entitled to judge journalistic work, while others argue that *not even* fellow journalists should be granted such authority: to them, the proof of the work is its enduring quality and its impact on the readership, studied and judged outside the chaotic arena of competition, through a sufficiently long time horizon.

In particular, Hampton found many who shared Merrill's concern, identifying the sticking point as the "inherent tensions of a profession whose claims to status derived from control over an 'open' public discourse, rather than arcane 'professional' knowledge" (p. 138). Several scholars tracked the negotiation of this tension back and forth along a line of professionalization that advances and recedes as journalists perceive that their credibility is threatened. Banning described a "crisis in credibility in the early twentieth century [which] prompted a visible drive that has been seen by some researchers as the first interest in journalistic professionalization" (1999, p. 157), and Demers & LeCam (2006) identified professionalization as the project of those who occupy institutional leadership roles, "while ordinary members of the organizations wanted to keep the journalistic occupation as free and open to newcomers as can be" (p. 665). Even Merrill agreed that "The rapid approach of this professional approach" comes in part from "journalists who naively think that professionalization will assure media responsibility and help close the credibility 'gap'" (p. 57).

In matching journalism's traits to a checklist of typical characteristics of professions, Reese alluded to the importance of shared identity, concluding that "We wish that journalists would adhere to certain roles ... because we think that doing so benefits the larger society" (2001, p. 175). Even if a consensus has never been reached on the formal definitional issue of whether journalism fits the profile of a profession, there nevertheless exists a *yearning*, from those within and outside the community of journalists, for professional behavior from its members. This set of behaviors includes conformity to expected roles, and it is from internal deliberation among professionals that the contours of those role expectations may be distilled.

The argument: NBC vs. the broadcast industry

Most of NBC's critics avoided the threshold question of whether to air the materials in the first place, since rival networks had also shown the footage. The exception was the Canadian Broadcasting Company, which refused to broadcast Cho's work at all, and whose news chief, Tony Burman, explained,

As I watched them last night, sickened as I'm sure most viewers were, I imagined what kind of impact this broadcast would have on similarly deranged people. In horrific but real ways, this is their 15 seconds of fame. I had this awful and sad feeling that there were parents watching these excerpts on NBC who were unaware they they will lose their children in some future copycat killing (Cobb, 2007, p. B4).

The attacks from other network heads targeted NBC's decision to keep the material in heavy rotation after the first news cycle was complete. Jon Klein, president of CNN, explained, "You could venture into the land of gratuitously overusing it, and we are being rigorous about that. It comes down to a balance between providing a platform to a madman and helping explain a riddle that has confounded many Americans" (Kurtz, 2007a, p. C01). John Moody, executive vice president of editorial content for Fox News, said "We believe that 18 hours after they were first broadcast and distributed via the Internet, our news viewers have had the opportunity to see the images and draw their own conclusions. We see no reason to continue assaulting the public with these disturbing and demented images" (Harper, 2007, p. A17). Paul Friedman, vice president of CBS News, called the repeated airings "...obviously offensive and disturbing, not only to the families and relatives but to lots and lots of viewers who are emotionally caught up with this. Why upset them all over again? The aim here is to make sure we never use this video as wallpaper" (Kurtz, 2007a, p. C01). And the sharpest condemnation of all came from ABC News

Senior Vice President Jeffrey Schneider, who charged, “Repeatedly airing the footage turns it into wallpaper at best, and pornography at worst. The video is viable for the first 24-hour news cycle, then its news value devolves” (Harper, 2007, p. A17).

Steve Capus, president of NBC’s news division, energetically defended both the decision and the decisionmaking process. In response to questions about airing the material at all, Capus developed two lines of defense. First, he cited the other networks’ decision, arguing “The news-value question is long gone. Every journalist is united on this. You can tell by their actions” (Carter, 2007, p. 21) and “Every one of our competitors, every newspaper made the same journalistic decision. The news value of this material cannot be disputed” (Kurtz, 2007a, p. C01). Later, he told CNN viewers that the video excerpts were the first evidence of Cho’s mental state, presaging reports from professors and classmates, and from Cho’s own classwork, that would become available in the days that followed:

...what we released was a photograph -- was videotape that showed someone on the edge, someone clearly about to boil over. And to me, it's akin to what we're reading now about what he was writing in his English department classes, in his essays, what he -- you know, all this videotape he was gathering up. He had been playing this for such a long time. The videotape underscores that. And I think it was representative of where he was.

(Kurtz & O’Brien, 2007, ¶¶ 93-96)

In a subsequent appearance on Keith Olbermann’s *Countdown*, Capus developed this line of defense into an emotional appeal that drew upon the randomness and inexplicability of Cho’s attack. Capus argued that seeing Cho’s face and hearing his words yielded the *only* available clues that might explain his actions:

And, you know, look, my feeling is about that that the immediate question that all of us had after this happened was, Why? And how in the world could this happen? Why would they target -- why would he target so many people? And this is as close as I think we're going to get to getting into his mind and trying to get to some of those answers. And I do think that that -- there is a responsibility to get that out, as wrenching as it is to hear and see his hateful words. (Olbermann, 2007, ¶¶ 64-67)

Responding to the more developed criticism of his choice to repeat the broadcasts, Capus launched into a painstakingly detailed description of the editing choices involved. He began by parrying accusations that he'd rushed the material to broadcast in order to score a scoop for his network. Instead, Capus explained, the NBC news staff had conducted a *lengthy* discussion of whether to do so, and how to proceed:

... we spent hours, hours, all day long. We didn't -- we didn't reveal to the world that we had this material as we worked on the editorial decisions. Everything from, should we run this, to should we release everything, as some of our competitors were screaming at us that we had an obligation to "release everything" (Kurtz & O'Brien, 2007, ¶¶ 99-100).

In some retellings, Capus' emphasis on the time spent to arrive at the right decision took on a reverent tone, painting a funereal solemnity around the discussion: "We went over it for seven and a half hours. We didn't rush it on the air. We weren't promoting it. We weren't trumpeting it all day. It was extraordinary, and that's how we treated it" (Carter, 2007, p. 21).

Capus further detailed the careful, non-sensational approach his staff took by describing their scrupulous efforts to cooperate fully with law enforcement. He told his CNN audience, "We were quietly working with the authorities every step of the way. They applauded us for our

handling of the matter” (Kurtz & O’Brien, 2007, ¶ 105), and explained further to Chris Matthews,

But the key is when it came in here, NBC security opened it and handled it appropriately and everybody who touched it wore gloves to keep everything intact. And we immediately contacted authorities and that set forward the chain of events. And we worked with the authorities this afternoon to make sure that they knew everything that we did. And they requested that we not release some of the information until they had a chance to take a look at it. And we honored that request. And that was the right thing to do. (Matthews et al., 2007, ¶ 30).

Finally, Capus supplied a thorough account of the editing choices that preceded the broadcast. He revealed that the first decision to limit the MSNBC coverage to no more than six minutes per hour was implemented the same evening as its first airing on *Nighty News* (Kurtz & O’Brien, 2007), and put the material aired in perspective against the material withheld:

I think we made the same decision again that every -- that all journalists made, which was that we were going to restrict the use. And to me, it's completely in sync with the original editorial decision we made. If you think that there was 25 minutes of videotape, we released such a small fraction. There's something like 43, 45 photographs. We released a handful. There's 23 pages of documents. We have released just some sampling of his words. We held that back because we didn't think it was appropriate to put everything out there. Then we would be guilty of being -- of playing into his hands, if you will, and just giving him the spotlight (Kurtz & O’Brien, 2007, ¶¶ 111-114).

Asked if some material had not yet been released, Capus replied, “Well, there`s definitely some things that I don`t think are appropriate to see the light of day. And we`re holding off on some of

that. And we're making determinations about what more can and should be released” (Olbermann, 2007, ¶¶ 65-66).

The climax of Capus' defense was a bifurcation of his audience into the sincere and the disingenuous. To angry Virginia Tech students, staff and faculty, Capus responded, "I'm not going to say we're oblivious to the comments coming out of the Virginia Tech community. We understand, we appreciate and we respect their concerns” (Kurtz, 2007a, p. C01) and “It is understandable and not surprising given the horrific experience they have all been through” (Carter, 2007, p. 21). The press release he approved began, “The pain suffered by the Virginia Tech community and indeed the entire country is immeasurable,” and ended with a reference to “our devoted efforts to remember and honor the victims and heroes of this tragic incident” (NBC News statement, 2007, ¶¶ 1, 3). On the other hand, to his colleagues at rival networks Capus first responded curtly that “I chalk that up to competitive silliness” (Carter, 2007, p. 21), but later permitted himself a longer and angrier response: “I'm stunned that people bang down our door at one moment, demanding we release it uninterrupted and without filter -- then question whether it should have been released in the first place. . . . I'm just stunned at the depths of absurdity and hypocrisy” (Kurtz, 2007b, p. C01). Throughout his defense, Capus offered only a single qualified concession: “Sometimes good journalism is bad public relations” (Kurtz & O'Brien, 2007, ¶ 99).

Good journalism, bad public relations?

Capus' concession may prove critical in exploring some of the more subtle argumentative dynamics that reveal the contours of professional identity channeling each side's arguments. In the first place, pinning down the relative position of journalism and public relations is tricky, since the two “have become so blurred it is hard to determine where the one stops and the other

starts” (Gower, 2007, p. 1). One thing is certain: the relationship is neither easy nor friendly. To one PR agent, “We're in a death grip together,” (Pittman, 2007, ¶ 16), while another onlooker observes that “For many journalists, public relations agents are the used car salesmen of the communications industry” (Trombly, 2002, p. 18). Friendly or not, the two occupations cohabit an enormous segment of one another’s activities. Marken (2003) explains that “journalists face the same struggle public relations professionals have satisfying both shareholders and their wide ranging publics” (p. 40), while Foley characterizes the distinction very simply: “It suits the PR industry to suggest that there is no real difference between journalism and its own branch of activity, or that the relationship is a symbiotic one. But there is a difference: one serves the public interest, the other a private interest” (2004, p. 76). Pieczka concurs: “Although PR is guided by the same values as journalism (see, for example, the IPR Code of Conduct), in practice these values may be refracted through the prism of client interests” (2006, p. 321). Extremely effective practitioners of each have moved into the counterpart field and found great success (Paluszek, 2002; Pieczka, 2006). And, ultimately, their prospects of success are intertwined, as Gower observes: “It’s probably fair to say that most major stories in the press, in every publication, and on every TV news program were placed or impeded or significantly shaped by public relations professionals” (2007, p. xiv). She concludes, “Public relations and journalism work together in a symbiotic, albeit troubled, relationship” (p. xvi). The prize at stake in these ongoing struggles is control of the message, both content and form, and four dominant influences are the levers each side struggles to pull in its own direction, to settle the epistemic question of “What shall be news?” in a fashion that advances its own interests.

The first is *selection*. A broadcast news director must begin by choosing among the available stories, ideally by resisting the pressure to crowd out newsworthy items in favor of, as

White describes it, “attention-grabbing stories for sensationalism” (2005, p. 661). He laments his worry that “... ‘news’ is what sells, impresses your rivals and has an impact on the readers or viewers. It normally comes in one of three forms – controversy (which can be positive or negative), emotion in the guise of ‘human interest’ stories, or the reporting of events” (p. 659). For Bishop (2004), this question should not simply be one of economics or ethics, but should rise to the level of *epistemic* work, bestowing upon collected information the public seal of reporting, of being entered into the collectively attended record of memory. Unfortunately, he warns, this authority has been all but abdicated: broadcast journalists have “completely ceded the authority to draw journalism’s cultural map to those who market news as ‘product.’ Epistemic authority in journalism . . . does not originate in the pages of professional journals; it emerges as the craft is practiced” (2004, p. 42). Those who market the news may include decisionmakers *inside* the organization who worry about its profitability, but are equally likely to be outside PR personnel, dedicated to advancing their clients’ interests. And some might argue that in placing marketing above news reporting, even those inside the organization have crossed professional lines and taken on the alter-ego.

And the reality is that the authority described does not rest exclusively within the grasp of the news organization, either in the reporting *or* marketing divisions, which is a primary source of the growing tension. The second function, once a story is identified as sufficiently distant from sensationalism to acquire the epistemic marker of “news,” is managing the relationship between reporter and *source*, to distill the necessary details that develop the reporting from breaking news into in-depth coverage that assists viewers in fully understanding the story’s meaning and significance. Gower insists that “Although journalists and public relations practitioners need each other, the idea that news can be managed threatens the journalistic ideals

of objectivity, truth, and balance,” and captures the one inescapable point of contact between PR and journalism in a simple, transformed relationship: “Journalists have always depended on sources. Without a source of information, the journalist has little to report. What the development of public relations brought to the table was, in effect, the professional source” (p. 2). Journalists seek to exercise enough control over the relationship with the source to succeed in filtering out the calculated bits that advance an agenda, but may struggle in that role as the sources become more powerful, aided by the strategic efforts of PR representatives.

The third influence is *editing*. Marken concedes that journalists “also have a major advantage over PR people. Good writing is the first requirement for getting a job in the field, not just another checkmark on the recruiter’s form” (2003, p. 40). This skill at writing has been operationalized for much of journalism’s history as “an ability to condense, summarize, and analyze,” which journalists of the day believed, Hampton reminds us, “could not be taught” (2005, p. 143). The notion that journalism was a *craft* included the premise that some reporters were temperamentally suited to take the essence of a story, the important core idea of a lengthy public statement, and present it as a compact, economical digest to the audience. Students of rhetoric will recognize this skill as *arrangement*, and as broadcast media have carved out space that once was occupied exclusively by print news, decisions about cutting, editing and sequencing have settled beside the condensing, summarizing and analyzing functions in the journalist’s toolbox. What a journalist seeks to exclude or condense may be the carefully-crafted message that the PR practitioner most wishes to include in the broadcast.

The fourth epistemic parameter held in place by the boundary tension between public relations and journalism is what Pech and Leibel (2006) identify as journalism’s “dominant view,” which

...understands the audience as social atoms. In so doing, journalism emphasizes potential differences in terms of social, political, moral, and aesthetic values The audience, from the perspective of mainstream journalism, is characterized in nonnormative, epistemic terms; humans are epistemic engines attempting, with the help of journalism, to acquire information about the world (pp. 149-150).

In the final stages of crafting and delivering the story, accounting for audience reception emerges from the pack of corrective forces and exerts its influence. Once the content has been selected, edited, and embellished with detail, then reframing to account for the expectations and needs of the viewers becomes

Identifying which of the permutations of good, bad, journalism and public relations best captures NBC's broadcast of Cho's manifesto requires drawing together the parameters identified in this section: the epistemic map, the editing process, the professionalized source and the atomized audience. Traces of these parameters plucked from the points of stasis separating Capus from his critics will yield clues to the current location of broadcast journalism along its pendulum-swing between profession and craft.

Mining the points of stasis

Capus' rivals aimed criticism at the selection function. They called Cho's product "disturbing and demented" and "pornography," attempted to strip it of the label of "news" and position it squarely among the sensational and the exploitative. Capus retorted that the question of newsworthiness "is long gone" and "cannot be disputed" because of other networks' decision to air the footage on their own programming. He positioned himself on the margin of the professional orientation, justifying his *actions* by noting their congruence with those of his fellows, but rejecting their *arguments*, their teachings, quite explicitly. They explained their

objections, while Capus simply appealed to their deeds, making it plain that, to him, identical decisions spoke louder than words. This nondiscursive proof located Capus near the boundary between profession and craft, plausibly generating a certain appeal to those who view journalism as an iconoclastic pursuit that is learned and improved through experience, not scholarship. His defense animated Bishop's claim that epistemic authority "emerges as the craft is practiced."

The other network heads also attempted to discredit the source, calling Cho a "madman" and "deranged." Capus' disputation of these charges involved less confrontation and more finesse. Precisely *because* Cho was mad and the actions were senseless, Capus argued, people had fewer resources for understanding what had happened and why, and were *more* starved for explanation, not less. Even if Cho's explanations were nonsensical, they were the only explanations in town; they might not move anyone toward closure, but they might clarify what exactly had happened, and how it had taken shape. The mourners' imaginations might be tamed and brought down to earth by a direct look at how miserable and irrational their tormentor was in direct confrontation. In this sense, Capus appealed to a helplessness, an inability to assert authority over his source and police the source's content, not solely because the source was no longer alive, but also because reasoning and persuasion would probably not have succeeded even prior to Cho's demise. NBC's coverage *studied* Cho, rather than engaging him; it gave him a platform, but in the same sense that a microbe is given a platform on a scientist's slide.

Rival news executives attacked NBC's editing, calling it "gratuitous overuse," "assaulting the public, "offensive and disturbing," and repeating one another in labeling it "wallpaper." Capus replied with specific references to the quantity of material received, and then non-specific references to quantity *used*, pointing out that of 25 minutes of videotape, 45 photos and 23 pages of documents, NBC's coverage included a "small fraction" of the video, a

“handful” of the photos and “some sampling” from the documents. He poured cold water on the accusations of gratuitous use and a sensory assault by emphasizing the many hours he waited before releasing the material. Without speaking precisely of his decision criteria or its output, he invoked its scale and deliberate pace to turn back accusations of hastiness and hunger for a scoop. He thus distanced himself and his organization from the characterization of being a newsroom run by the ad execs and the accountants: if this was marketing, it was marketing that showed remarkable restraint.

Finally, Capus’ critics charged him with inadequate concern for the vulnerable position of the audience, made up of “families and relatives [and] lots and lots of viewers who are emotionally caught up with this.” He replied in conciliatory terms, accepting the anger of people who were directly impacted by the shootings, but also gently writing off their complaints as eruptions of grief, rather than reasoned criticism, and in the same breath damning the other network decisionmakers as insincere and guilty of causing the audience the same pain. This concession to the audience that a certain amount of hurt might have been unavoidable, however regrettable, is the clearest antecedent for his concession that “good journalism is bad public relations.”

At each point of stasis, the charge took the form of *labeling*, and Capus’ rejoinder diverged into *positioning*. The heads of ABC, CBS, CNN, FOX and CBC each spoke briefly, bearing as they did the nonreciprocal burden of addressing one co-arguer, and their brief remarks affixed labels to the material and the quality of the decisionmaking. Capus in each case purported to demonstrate the labels’ inaccuracy by placing them in contexts that revealed their misapplication, calling his decision output almost indistinguishable from his colleagues’, his

decision process both thorough and properly weighted *against* publication, and the source noteworthy precisely because of the enigmatic quality of Cho's actions and mental state.

Conclusion

As journalists, both print and broadcast, wrestle with fluctuating credibility and increasingly skillful manipulators of sources, they continue to shoulder the duty of fixing a line between what may be identified as news and reported, and what must be exposed as sensationalism and discredited. The constitution of their work about the disclosure of any information of general interest to the public impedes their adoption of the trappings, protections and perks of recognized professions, but is nevertheless insufficient to drive them away entirely from the hunger for autonomy and the commitment to public service that characterize those pursuits. Those powerful and opposing forces leave journalism adrift between profession and craft, and thus quite vulnerable to endless dilemmas which may force decisions that are unbalanced and unbalancing, and appear to betray their values.

The material supplied by Seung-Hui Cho in the wake of the Virginia Tech shooting, and broadcast by NBC news on the authority of Steve Capus and the NBC news staff, may have been news but certainly sparked a sensation; may have been edited but certainly struck many onlookers as excessive; may have come directly from the source, but certainly repelled many audience members as clearing a channel for the ravings of a madman; may have been the only cure for intolerable ignorance, but still stirred up fear and hurt among those still recovering from Cho's attack. Capus' team attempted to exert control over source, content, frame and audience, but found, as so many times before, that each element exerted force that they had not fully mastered.

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